

Bahia Palace

La Bahia is one of the sumptuous Moroccan palaces of the 20th century. It was founded in 1866 under the order of Abu Imrane Mussa Ben Ahmed Ben Mbarek, chamberlain of Sultan Sidi Muhammad Ben Abderrahmane (1859-1873) and Grand Vizir of Sultan Al Hassan the First (1873-1894). The palace was later enlarged by his son Ahmed Ben Mussa known as Ba-Hmad, chamberlain, Grand Vizir and Regent of Sultan Mulay Abdelaziz (1894-1908). Under the French Protectorate (1912-1956), the Bahia served as the headquarters of the General Residence of Marshal Lyautey and after the Independence, it was transferred to the Royal domain and opened to the public in 1998, under the supervision of the Ministry of Culture as a listed national historical monument by the Dahir (royal decree) of December 21, 1924.

The palace extends over a total area estimated at 8 hectares including 37,100 m² of buildings. Indeed, it was from 1894 that Ba Hmad ordered the expansion of his father's residence by the construction of new buildings designed by the architect Muhammad b. Makki Masfiwi (1857-1926), expert and qualified grand master of crafts know-how. The work lasted six years and included the expansion of the large Riad (core of the palace) and the construction of the small Riad, a small marble courtyard, the development of the large Riad and the private pavilion as well as a series of annex buildings.

The Bahia is a jewel of Moroccan architecture, a collection of artisanal know-how and an essential testimony to the Moroccan art of living among powerful families of the 19th century.